

Development of Slope Detection ASIC for On-Chip Current Sensing in Voltage Converters

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Abstract

This research centers on the design and analysis of an on-chip indirect approach aimed at estimating the output load current in a DC-DC flyback converter. This indirect method for estimating electric current relies on assessing the slope of the output voltage from the converter on the external filter capacitor during discharge phases. Consequently, this slope data can be effectively harnessed to control the converter's switches. The proposed circuit operates on a power supply of 1.2 V and was designed using standard 65 nm CMOS technology. The designed slope detector circuit has the capability of measuring current within the range of one to hundreds of milliamperes. Given its predominantly digital nature, the circuit provides inherent robustness against variations in process, temperature, and supply voltage.

Keywords: current sensing methods; voltage drop; slope detector; voltage converters; low-power and low-voltage design; CMOS technology

1. Introduction

In the present era, achieving low power consumption has become a paramount requirement in design of integrated circuits (ICs) and complex system-on-chip (SoC) configurations. Contemporary advancements and research in the realm of portable electronic devices predominantly concentrate on design principles towards energy savings, operation under reduced voltage conditions, and integration of different mixed-signal circuits and/or systems into a single

monolithic chip. Generally, analog circuits tend to be the most power-hungry subsystems within SoCs. As a result, in the majority of instances, having knowledge regarding the specific load or current consumption can provide an efficient method to lowering the power dissipation of the entire system. Furthermore, advances in IC manufacturing are welcome but lead to sophisticated technologies with notable deviations in process characteristics. As a consequence, ensuring the IC performance with resilience to process-voltage-temperature (PVT) variations becomes one of the most demanding endeavors for both IC designers and researchers. This concern becomes particularly critical when addressing circuits requiring a high degree of precision.

The obtained electric current load can serve as a control parameter for other circuits within the entire system. One potential application of utilizing the electric current value as a control signal is in the regulation of a DC-DC converter. Several types of converters are available, but this study places particular emphasis on the flyback DC-DC converter. This type falls under the category of a straightforward configuration of an isolated converter, commonly utilized as the power supply circuit in cellphones, laptops, PCs, TVs, and various other electronic devices [1, 2].

2. Background and motivation

For purpose of effective regulation and control of flyback converters, the load current should be sensed. In on-chip current sensing methods, the usual strategy entails directly measuring current using a sensing element. This commonly incorporates elements such as a shunt resistor, a MOS transistor configured as a resistor, or a sensing transistor linked in parallel with the power MOS device [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. More comprehensive details regarding the properties and features of these techniques are provided in [5]. Nevertheless, the primary drawbacks associated with direct measurement approaches are diminished accuracy and relatively elevated power losses across the sensing element. Conversely, indirect methodologies provide the opportunity to detect current without requiring an extra sensing element connected in series. In this way, they present lossless options for an on-chip measurement of electric current. These techniques leverage alternative electrical parameters that are directly correlated to the sensed current. Therefore, indirect methods do not affect the performance of the measured circuit despite introducing an extra measurement hardware. The comparison between direct measurement and indirect measurement approaches is shown in Fig. 1. Comparison table

including advantages and disadvantages in comparison with other work is shown in Table. 1

Figure 1: Comparison of direct and indirect measurement approaches.

Table 1: Advantages and disadvantages of the proposed method in comparison to other works.

Advantages	Disadvantages
no sensing element needed no ADC needed high power efficiency resistance to PVT variations low power	low accuracy window comparator

This paper introduces the slope detector circuit designed in 65 nm CMOS technology. This circuit serves as indirect on-chip current measurement and subsequent control of the flyback DC-DC converter. Section two elaborates on the fundamental concept underpinning the devised slope detector. The simulation-derived outcomes are displayed in the third section, while the actual measured results are exhibited in the fourth. The utilization of the indirect measurement approach is outlined in section number five, and the paper culminates with the drawn conclusions in the last section.

3. Proposed Indirect Sensing

As mentioned above, many portable electronic devices use flyback DC-DC converter as a power source due to its electrical isolation and simple topology. Under light-load conditions or standby mode, flyback converter usually works in so-called "burst" mode [9, 10]. In order to regulate the converter output voltage and control the voltage ripple, the output current and converter voltage need to be estimated. For this purpose, direct sensing approaches using auxiliary winding of the transformer are usually employed. However, the typical flyback converter topology includes an output bypass capacitor to reduce voltage ripple at the converter output. The output current can therefore, be estimated indirectly just by sensing a voltage drop across the capacitor. This is the main idea behind such an indirect method of measuring the output current of flyback DC-DC converter working in the burst mode [11]. The basic topology of flyback converter and typical waveform of the signals are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively [12]. It can be observed that the burst mode contains two phases: burst-on and burst-off periods. During the burst-on time, the output voltage is boosted to the requested value. On the other hand, during the burst-off time, the converter output voltage decreases due to current flowing from output capacitor to the load. Hence, the output current of converter can be sensed during this phase indirectly by sensing the output voltage. It is important to note that output voltage ripple can be defined by reference voltages (V_{REF_H} and V_{REF_L}), which are included in control circuitry of the converter.

Figure 2: Typical topology of flyback converter

The proposed sensing approach presented is based on the idea described above. In discharging phase of the output capacitor (burst-off time), slope of the output voltage is sensed within defined voltage and time windows. In

Figure 3: Flyback operation in the burst mode

Figure 4, one can observe the fundamental principle of the proposed indirect measurement method. In this setup, the output voltage, indicative of the output load current, is sensed through an external capacitor, transforming the load current into a voltage value. This approach is based on the utilization of a substantial bypass capacitor C_O , an inherent component of the converter. The mathematically expressed load current I_{sens} definition is as follows:

$$I_{sens} = \frac{V_{sens}}{R_L} \cdot e^{\frac{-t}{R_L C_O}} \approx \frac{V_{sens}}{R_L}, \quad (1)$$

where V_{sens} is the output voltage, R_L is the load resistor and C_O is the output capacitor (see Figure 2). Assuming $t/R_L C_O \rightarrow 0$, the output voltage undergoes a linear change over time with resistive load. This condition is ensured either by carrying out current sensing in a short time interval or by having a substantial time constant of capacitor discharge, $t/R_L C_O$. Consequently, if either of these conditions is met, it becomes possible to indirectly detect electric current by observing the slope of the voltage across capacitor C_O during its discharging phase. The defined time interval for measurement is determined by two voltage references, namely V_{REF_H} and V_{REF_L} (represented as the voltage window ΔV in Figure 4). Under these conditions, the corresponding electric current can be expressed as:

$$I_{sens} = C_O \cdot \frac{\Delta V}{\Delta T} = \frac{V_{REF_L} - V_{REF_H}}{t_L - t_H}, \quad (2)$$

It is crucial to highlight that the precision of the proposed current estimation method may be affected by variations in process, temperature, and supply

Figure 4: Output voltage slope detection principle.

voltage (PVT). These fluctuations are not considered in Equation (5). However, during the circuit design phase, PVT variations were fully taken into account, and the developed circuit was designed to be robust against these variations, especially its critical parts, such as voltage comparators, oscillator and voltage reference circuit. The voltage reference was designed as temperature independent, and to make it robust against the process fluctuations, the digital trimming approach was employed. In order to minimize the input offset voltage of comparators, proper layout matching techniques were carefully applied. The oscillator topology, used in the proposed circuit for slope detection, exhibits low temperature coefficient. All these techniques and many others were used to reduce the undesired impact of PVT variations on the circuit overall performance.

Figure 5 depicts a block diagram of the proposed circuit for slope detection so-called Slope Detector (SD). The main principle is based on counting the number of pulses in a defined time interval, which is given by reference voltage values (V_{REF_H} and V_{REF_L}). Reference voltages are appropriate set to be compared with the output voltage of converter. The output voltage is sensed by a voltage divider connected to the output of DC-DC converter (pin labeled as V_{sens} is the voltage divider output). This voltage is monitored by a window comparator created by the combination of comparators K1 and K2. The input comparators are constructed using a standard topology which incorporates an adjustable hysteresis, providing protection against undesired oscillations and glitches. The output from the window comparator is directed to the component named DRIVER_ SD, which regulates the switching behavior of the counter. The counter functions on a CLK signal

with frequency of 500 kHz (taking into account the external input frequency of 1 MHz and the multiplexer output transferred from input $in1$). To extend the measuring range of slope, the switching frequency of the counter can be reduced by leveraging the built-in multiplexer. While this simple feature enables the sensing of a broader range of currents, it simultaneously reduces the accuracy of the measurement system by lowering the counter switching frequency.

Following the cessation of counting by the counter, the resulting value is compared with the values stored in the Look-Up-Table (LUT).

Figure 5: Block diagram of the slope detector circuit.

The slope value of the output sensed voltage ranges from 10 up to 150, and the counter switching frequencies are set to 500 kHz, 250 kHz, 125 kHz, and 62.5 kHz. The achieved calculated results represent the ideal finite counter value without any measurement errors considered. These calculation results, obtained using equations (3) and (4), are shown in Table 2. In calculations, we take into account the specified time window length Δt , the change in output voltage ΔV (set to 60 mV), and the counter switching frequency f_{start} .

$$\Delta t = \frac{\Delta V}{SLOPE} \quad (3)$$

Table 2: Calculated conversion table between the switching frequency, the slope of sensed output voltage and the finite value of counter.

SLOPE	Counter frequency [kHz]			
	500	250	125	62,5
10	3000	1500	750	375
20	1500	750	375	187.5
30	1000	500	250	125
40	750	375	187.5	93.8
50	600	300	150	75
60	500	250	125	62.5
70	428.6	214.3	107.1	53.6
80	375	187.5	93.8	46.9
90	333.3	166.7	83.3	41.7
100	300	150	75	37.5
110	272.7	136.4	68.2	34.1
120	250	125	62.5	31.3
130	230.8	115.4	57.7	28.8
140	214.3	107.1	53.6	26.8
150	200	100	50	25

$$Count = \frac{\Delta t}{\frac{1}{f_{start}}} \quad (4)$$

Given that comparators are employed for measurement, the entire measurement system is susceptible to manufacturing process variations, which can notably impact the input offset of the comparators. Consequently, the delay introduced by both comparators may impact the overall accuracy of the proposed measurement method. Thus, equation (5) requires an extension, as follows:

$$I_{sens} = C_O \cdot \frac{\Delta V}{\Delta T} = \frac{V_{REF_L} - V_{REF_H} \pm \Delta V_{off}}{t_L - t_H \pm \Delta t_d}, \quad (5)$$

where, ΔV_{off} and Δt_d represent the disparities in input offset voltage and transition delay of comparators (K1 and K2), respectively. These two parameters can primarily be influenced by the mismatch between the comparators. This mismatch, stemming from variations in the manufacturing process, can result in performance inconsistencies of individual components. Consequently, variations in the input offset voltage and delay of the comparators can occur, impacting the accuracy and reliability of the measurement method.

Figure 6: Operation of the SD circuit.

The waveforms shown in Figure 6 illustrate the sequence of signals of the measurement system. At the uppermost part of the figure, one can observe the inputs of the comparator reference voltages (V_{REF_H} and V_{REF_L}). In the middle section of the figure, the outputs of the window comparator circuit are depicted as $COMP_H$ and $COMP_L$, and finally, at the bottom of the figure, one will find the clock signal (CLK) and the output of the counter (Count). The counter value is reset to zero using a global external reset and its value incremented with each rising edge of the clock signal CLK. In the middle figure, the outputs from comparators K1 (green color) and K2 (red color) are depicted. We have distinguished comparators with set hysteresis and without hysteresis using dashed and solid lines, respectively. As we employed non-clocked comparators, an error denoted as Δt_{clk} might occur. The maximum potential error that can occur is the discrepancy between the rising edge of the clock signal and the falling edge comparator

K1 labeled as COMP_H. This value may be less than one clock period. A similar error arises at the conclusion of the measurement window between the rising edge of comparator K2 labeled as COMP_L and the rising edge of the clock signal. The hysteresis of comparators K1 and K2, denoted as ΔV_1 and ΔV_2 , respectively, and both comparators share the same hysteresis value. As a result of this hysteresis effect, delays named Δt_1 and Δt_2 will be present in the output signals of comparators K1 and K2, respectively. The comparator outputs and the counter values, with their delays, are depicted using dashed lines in middle and bottom graphs, respectively. The differences between Δt_1 of comparator K1 and Δt_2 of comparator K2 are consistently maintained within a nanosecond range, even across various process corners. This slight difference is considered acceptable as it does not significantly affect the measurement time window.

4. Simulation Results

In this section, the simulation results of the proposed slope detector circuit are presented. In the simulation results, we incorporated the impact of the production process variations, conducting analyses using both corner and Monte Carlo (MC) analyses. The temperature range considered in all simulations was set between -20°C and $+85^\circ\text{C}$. In Figure 7, one can observe a dependence of the counter finite value on the sensed voltage slope. These results were obtained from both Corner Analysis and Monte Carlo. As mentioned, the proposed SD operates by counting clock pulses within a defined time window, rendering it robust against variations induced by fabrication process fluctuations. The primary sensitivity lies in any mismatch among the devices constituting comparators K1 and K2. The results depicted in Figure 7 and Figure 8 reveal that device mismatch introduces fluctuations in the finite counter value, with a standard deviation of ± 6 pulses counted by the counter. Accounting for $\pm 3\sigma$ variations, the recorded pulses can range from 138 to 172, with a mean value of 159. This parameter signifies the overall error of the proposed approach, encompassing the mismatch of all devices employed in the slope detector circuit. The second part of the measurement error is caused by Δt_{clk} (see Figure 6) and explained in the previous section. In Figure 9, Δt_{clk} error over the process corners for slope of 150 V/s is shown. It can be observed that Δt_{clk} can exhibit variations across different process corners, leading to a measurement error of approximately $2\ \mu\text{s}$. If we considered the input frequency of 1 MHz , this implies that in a

Figure 7: Dependence of the counter finite value on the sensed voltage slope.

Figure 8: Monte Carlo analysis: for slope = 150 V/s.

process corner, Δt_{clk} can have an undesirable impact on the finite counter value, resulting in the addition of 1 to 2 extra pulses counted by the counter. It is essential to highlight that Δt_{clk} was examined for various slope values, and in most cases, the maximum measurement error of $2 \mu s$ was observed. Figure 10 illustrates the results of Monte Carlo analysis for the Δt_{clk} error at a slope of 150 V/s. Considering variations of $\pm 3\sigma$, the value of Δt_{clk} can vary within the range from $1.512 \mu s$ to $2.506 \mu s$, with a mean value of $1.955 \mu s$. The maximum current error caused by the Δt_{clk} effect was determined using equations (6) and (7).

In these equations, I_{err} represents the calculated current error, C_O is the value of the external capacitor, ΔV denotes the change in sensed output voltage, Δt is the duration of time window, and Δt_{clk} represents the maximum

Figure 9: Δt_{clk} error for slope of 150 V/s.

Figure 10: Monte Carlo analysis: Δt_{clk} error for slope = 150 V/s.

error caused by the asynchronous operation of comparators K1 and K2. If the counter switching frequency remains constant during the measurement process, Δt_{clk} can be calculated as $2(\frac{1}{f_{start}})$, where f_{start} is the counter switching frequency. The calculated measurement current error I [mA] with a constant switching frequency is illustrated in Figure 11. The lowest measurement current error was achieved with the maximum switching frequency of 500 kHz, which corresponds to 1 MHz input frequency of the measurement system.

$$I_{err} = C_O \frac{\Delta V}{\Delta t + 2\Delta t_{clk}} \quad (6)$$

$$I_{err} = C_O \frac{\Delta V}{\Delta t + 2(\frac{1}{f_{start}})} \quad (7)$$

The current measurement error when the counter switching frequency gets changed is calculated using equation (8), where f_{Start} represents the initial switching frequency of 500 kHz, and f_{Stop} is the changed switching frequency that depends on the SLOPE of sensed output voltage and it is set to determine the range corresponding to the switching frequency. The most favorable results were obtained with the switching frequency changed from 500 kHz to 250 kHz, as shown in Figure 12.

$$I = C_O \frac{\Delta V}{\Delta t + \left(\frac{1}{f_{Start}} + \frac{1}{f_{End}} \right)} \quad (8)$$

To rigorously assess the reliability of the suggested slope detector, variations

Figure 11: Calculated current measurement error for different values of counter frequency.

in the time window were scrutinized across all process corners and complete temperature range. Figure 13 shows the time window variation for different slope values. As one can observe, the absolute value of the time window differs for various slope values, but it remains consistent across different process corners. However, devices mismatch within K1 and K2 can introduce additional measurement errors, necessitating the use of sophisticated layout techniques. Monte Carlo analysis of the time window variation for a slope of 150 V/s is depicted in Figure 14. The time window value can fluctuate within the range from 369.1 μs to 424.7 μs , with a mean value of 398.041 μs . For this analysis, variations of $\pm 3\sigma$ was considered. Figure 15 presents a physical layout of the developed slope detector circuit. The implemented layout has dimensions of 62 μm x 265 μm , resulting in an occupied chip area of 0.016 mm². Both comparators significantly contribute to the total

Figure 12: Calculated current measurement error for counter frequency change within a certain range during measurement.

area. On the other hand, they also incorporate additional functionalities, such as hysteresis tuning and calibration features, necessary for testing the fabricated chip samples.

Figure 13: Variations of time window over process corners.

Figure 14: Monte Carlo analysis: Variations of time window.

Figure 15: Layout of the developed slope detector.

5. ASIC evaluation and measurement results

An experimental ASIC was fabricated using a general-purpose 65 nm CMOS process. The required measurement circuits were integrated onto the same chip alongside the ASIC system. Vital and significant points of the ASIC were linked to external measurement circuits that were implemented on the test PCB board. A developed digital logic unit controls the entire system on the chip and the measurement process. The presence of this control logic facilitates the experimental verification process and also reduces the number of required package pins, resulting in greater efficiency. Additionally, the control logic has the capability of adjusting a specific parameters of the circuit, such as hysteresis in comparators K1 and K2. The block diagram of the entire measurement setup is depicted in Figure 16. For this setup, the following equipment was used: Keysight InfiniVision DSOX2054 4-channel digital storage oscilloscope with 5 GSPS and 500 MHz of bandwidth, Keysight 33600A Series Waveform Generator, and Rohde & Schwarz HMC 8043 3-channel power supply. Table 3 displays the measured conversion table,

Figure 16: Block diagram of measurement setup.

which shows the relationship between slope of the output sensed voltage, the input switching frequency of the counter, and the corresponding finite counter value. The input conditions used for measurements were identical to those used in simulations. The slope was varied from 10 to 150, and the switching frequency was set to 500 kHz, 250 kHz, and 125 kHz, respectively. Additionally, an adaptive frequency was used, depending on the set range corresponding to the specific slope value. When comparing the results obtained from simulation to the measured results, some differences can be observed in the counter values. These differences may be caused by various factors, such as process tolerances, noise, and other influences. The main source of error within the measurement is likely to be the mismatch between comparators K1 and K2, as this can affect the accuracy of SD circuit.

To identify the underlying reasons for the error, conducting a comprehensive investigation of the implemented comparators in the SD circuit through precise measurements of delay and hysteresis characteristics is of utmost importance. To verify the results, we performed the measurement for five different chip samples. The measured time delays of comparators K1 and K2 are depicted in Table 4. The error of time window, caused by the time delay of comparators, was calculated by determining the time difference between the rising edge of comparator K1 and the falling edge of comparator

Table 3: Comparison of measured and simulated results (Relation between counter frequency, SLOPE of sensed output voltage, and finite value of counter).

SLOPE	Measured results				Simulated results		
	500 Hz	250 Hz	125 Hz	Adaptive frequency	500 Hz	250 Hz	125 Hz
10	3122	1338	826	808	3000	1500	750
20	1456	949	476	627	1500	750	375
30	1169	645	333	555	1000	500	250
40	911	438	241	510	750	375	187
50	774	389	194	470	600	300	150
60	623	332	164	438	500	250	125
70	534	256	133	407	428	214	107
80	481	241	122	395	375	187	93
90	443	210	111	379	333	166	83
100	389	193	98	350	300	150	75
110	348	175	88	332	272	136	68
120	322	134	82	318	250	125	62
130	298	149	76	302	230	115	57
140	272	136	69	277	214	107	53
150	246	124	64	249	200	100	50

K2. This time difference represents the delay of time window, and can impact the overall accuracy of slope measurement. The worst-case is observed with sample number three, where the time difference between the rising edge of comparator K1 and the falling edge of comparator K2 results in the largest error in the time window duration of 994 ns. Such a value of delay has only a negligible impact on measurement results, especially when the input frequency of 500 kHz is used. In such cases, the delay is relatively small compared to the period of input signal, and its influence on the measurement accuracy can be neglected. In Table 5 and Table 6,

Table 4: Time delay of comparators K1 and K2.

	COMP_L Delay [us]		COMP_H Delay [us]		Delay error [ns]
	Rising edge	Falling edge	Rising edge	Falling edge	COMP_L(Rising edge)-COMP_H(Falling edge)
Chip1	1.613	1.165	2.822	1.089	524
Chip2	2.054	1.1	1.89	1.170	884
Chip3	2	1.028	1.765	1.006	994
Chip4	1.9	1.034	1.983	1.056	846
Chip5	1.388	1.208	3.282	0.750	638

one can find the measurement results of hysteresis for comparators COM_L (K1) and COMP_H (K2), respectively. Hysteresis was measured for the slope values of 10 and 150, encompassing both the rising and falling edges of the comparators. The total error in the finite counter value, taking into account the switching frequency and the slope, is presented in Table 7. These errors represent variations in the width of time window due to differences in hysteresis between rising edge COM_L and falling edge of COMP_H. The best outcomes were achieved in case of SLOPE 10 for Chip1 and Chip5, and SLOPE 150 for Chip4 and Chip5. As one can observe, reducing the switching frequency leads to a decrease in the total estimation error. However, it is important to note that this reduction in error comes at the cost of estimation accuracy.

Table 5: Measurement results: hysteresis of comparator $COMP_L$ across chip samples.

	COMP_L							
	HYS - SLOPE 10				HYS - SLOPE 150			
	Rising edge		Falling edge		Rising edge		Falling edge	
	HYS [mV]	Time [us]	HYS [mV]	Time [us]	HYS [mV]	Time [us]	HYS [mV]	Time [us]
Chip1	15.2	1320	19.2	1680	7	36	14	87
Chip2	10.4	944	14.8	1340	9.6	64	17.2	110
Chip3	10	840	16.4	1370	3.2	256	9.6	780
Chip4	10	836	15.6	1270	8.8	49	17.2	106
Chip5	6.4	560	9.6	860	5.5	27	12.8	84

Table 6: Measurement results: hysteresis of comparator $COMP_H$ across the evaluated chip samples.

	COMP_H							
	HYS - SLOPE 10				HYS - SLOPE 150			
	Rising edge		Falling edge		Rising edge		Falling edge	
	HYS [mV]	Time [us]	HYS [mV]	Time [us]	HYS [mV]	Time [us]	HYS [mV]	Time [us]
Chip1	20	1620	13.6	1250	20.8	140	11.6	74
Chip2	11.2	880	5.6	520	12.4	84	3.6	24
Chip3	7.6	700	2.4	160	10	62	1.6	8
Chip4	14	1200	10	920	16	101	7.6	50
Chip5	8	680	6	490	11.2	70	4	20

Table 8 shows correlation of the finite counter value for results obtained by simulation, post-layout simulation, and chip sample measurement. While post-layout simulation results of the developed slope detector with parasitics correlate excellently with simulations, chip sample measurement results exhibit

Table 7: Error in the finite counter value measured on five chip samples for the different switching frequency and slope values.

	SLOPE 10			SLOPE 150		
	500 kHz	250 kHz	125 kHz	500 kHz	250 kHz	125 kHz
Chip1	35	17.5	8.75	19	9.5	4.75
Chip2	212	106	53	20	10	5
Chip3	340	170	85	124	62	31
Chip4	42	21	10.5	0.5	0.25	0.125
Chip5	35	17.5	8.75	3.5	1.75	0.875

certain discrepancies. This may be due to sensitivity of the circuit to setting of critical building blocks during the evaluation process (e.g. oscillator or comparator, which hysteresis setting may have some effect on the measurement). Therefore, further effort will be paid to the slope detector prototype evaluation and analysis of obtained measurement results. However, we would like to underline that the presented method is only aimed at estimation of the converter output current, where a certain range of the output current is sufficient for the efficient control of the power switch.

6. Conclusions

A novel indirect strategy for on-chip current sensing, utilizing measurement of the output voltage slope, is introduced. However, it is essential to guarantee a high degree of device matching to minimize discrepancies leading to the measurement error and to enhance the overall precision of current measurement. Thus, further improvement can be reached by employing calibration/trimming of the input voltage offset of the comparator circuits employed in the proposed SD. The time delay of comparator suggests that this delay has no significant influence on the measurement accuracy and can be considered negligible. Nevertheless, the varying hysteresis values of comparators may lead to differences in the width of time window, which becomes the cause of notable measurement inaccuracies. The dissimilarities in comparator hysteresis could be caused by inadequate device matching or result from variations in the manufacturing process. The proposed measurement method and the designed SD circuit have the potential to find utility within a DC-DC converter system, providing the measurement of load current or helping to approximate the output current. This application can significantly enhance control of the entire converter and

Table 8: Comparison the finite counter value obtained from simulation, post-layout simulation, and measurement at 125 kHz switching frequency and for different slope values.

SLOPE	Simulation	Post-layout simulation	Measurement
10	750	751	826
20	375	375	476
30	250	249	333
40	187	187	241
50	150	149	194
60	125	124	164
70	107	107	133
80	93	92	122
90	83	83	111
100	75	75	98
110	68	67	88
120	62	62	82
130	57	58	76
140	53	52	69
150	50	50	64

improve its conversion efficiency. As for the future, our primary goal will include enhancing the design of comparators, aiming to the improvement of durability and precision of the applied indirect technique for electric current measurement.

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